

Smart Farming and Auto-pumping Monitoring System

Kaushik Das¹, Ava Rani Paul², Asmita Bag², Prof. Shyam K. Mondal³

¹B.Sc, Sem VI, Department of Computer Science, Bangabashi Morning college,

²B.Sc, Sem VI, Department of Computer Science, Maharaja Manindra Chandra College,

³Department of Computer Science, Syamaprasad College, to.shyam.k.mondal@gmail.com

Abstract - Smart Farming and auto-pumping Monitoring System whose main moto is to reduce the overhead of monitoring a farm every day. A farmer has to check the moisture of the soil and has to pump water himself. After checking the soil, the recognition of the perfect moisture for the farming and pumping water, can be difficult for him/her. So we are creating small project to check the moisture and auto pump water to the soil through the motor whenever there is low moisture in it. And lastly keeping a track of the pumping of water and the soil moisture for further betterment.

Keywords - Soil Moisture; Transistor; Volumetric Content; Auto pumping; Conductors;

1.0 System Requirements:

Arduino Uno

Soil moisture sensor(probe)

Arduino Uno (microcontroller), Soil moisture sensing module, Motor (12V) , ESP8266 (a wifi module which is used to fetch and the data from device to database), Transistor (used for regulating the current to control the Motor).

Design & Methodology-

2.0 Sensing the soil Moisture:

This **soil moisture sensor module** is used to detect the moisture of the soil. It measures the volumetric content of water inside the soil and gives us the moisture level as output. The fork-shaped probe with two exposed conductors acts as a variable resistor, whose resistance varies with the soil's moisture content. This resistance varies inversely with soil moisture:

- The more water in the soil, the better the conductivity and the lower the resistance.
- The less water in the soil, the lower the conductivity and thus the higher the resistance.

These two probes are used to pass the current through the soil and then the sensor reads the resistance to get the moisture values. The sensor produces an output voltage according to the resistance, which by measuring we can determine the soil moisture level.

3.0 Circuit Diagram:-

Switching on the pump:

In this part we use transistor and the motor. Transistor will be connected with Arduino (microcontroller) and then the other side will be connected with the motor.

Transistor: It will generate the motor as a switch.

Motor: It will pump water to the soil automatically.

At first we will take a threshold value of voltage which will say if the soil is moistured or not then according to the output voltage the transistor will generate the motor with the help of that threshold value.

If the soil becomes perfect moistured the transistor will automatically turn off the motor.

4.0 Future Scope

1. Water pumping in the huge area by any person can be a difficult function. So in future this can be effective in the purpose of agriculture.
2. The primary function of our project is to have a landscape irrigation system which ensures that water is spread regularly, timely and evenly throughout any given landscape.
3. It is being made in very low cost. So that can be effective for farmers
4. In the case of gardener, this system is very useful.

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